

Forum's Information Extraction Algorithms

Saeed Sarencheh, Bahram Sadeghi Bigham, Vidyasagar Potdar, Bahman Ghandchi, Nazanin Firoozeh, Elham A. Yegane
{sarenche, b_sadeghi_b, b.ghandchi, n_firoozeh, yeganeh}@iasbs.ac.ir,
Department of Computer Science and IT, Institute for Advanced Studies in Basic Sciences (IASBS), Zanjan, Iran.
Vidyasagar.Potdar@cbs.curtin.edu.au, Curtin University of technology

Abstract—Everyday lots of people surf the different web pages especially different forums. Nowadays, forums are known as information board in electronic society which announcements, interest topics, request are wrote there and also user can discuss to each other there. Therefore forums represent a huge information from different topics that sent by users as posts or threads. These areas that lots of people submitted a huge number of posts help spammer to reach their aims. So, the best way against spammer is detect spammer users id in forums base on user's behavior. Information extraction is tools that make possible to check post's content and author's id. The information extraction is challengeable task. There are some software that can extract information from specific forums software (like as phpBB, SMF, vBulletin).we introduced some IE algorithms in this paper. Semi-automatic and automatic algorithms are describe in this paper.

Keywords-component; forums; semi-automatic algorithms; automatic algorithm; spam; discussion board

I. INTRODUCTION

Forum is a place that members with different interests can interact in order to participate in discussions, share information and find out important issues. Since forum is used in education, health care, community, business contexts and so on [1], planning a powerful forum is very important.

For example [Http://discussion.forum.nokia.com/forum/](http://discussion.forum.nokia.com/forum/) is a commercial forum where people can share their experiences about different series of Nokia platforms. Other one (<http://opcwacademicforum.org/>) is an academic forum that introduces workshops and has a schedule about tasks done in workshop's days.

Like these there are millions of other forums on the web. We estimate that there are at least 97 million forums on the Web as of November 2009.

These forums are hosted on a number of different platforms or software; the famous ones are SMF, phpBB and vBulletin. In Australian domains these are used more often than any other open source software's. All the forums are predominantly programmed in PHP and use

MySQL as a database. phpBB is currently supported by six core developers, more than 40 team members, and 250,000 registered users [2]. SMF also is an open source package which is highly extensible and flexible. It is currently supported by several teams, including a customization team, development team, documentation team, support team, marketing team, project management team and an internationalization team. Compared to phpBB and SMF, vBulletin is a proprietary platform allows forum's owners improve their service to the forum's users. These three forum platforms represent the most popular forum platforms used on the web these days [3].

As it is seen, all these forums contain a wide range of information that is very important and helpful for users. Since forums contain valuable opinions from different people on different topics from different fields, forums play an important role to represent rich source of information. Therefore spammers make use of this valuable tool to achieve their goals. In recent years, spammers have exploited legitimate website security vulnerability to conceal themselves from anti-spam filters and genuine users, for example by injecting junk content into the web site [4]. Immoderate growth of the junk content is degrading the quality of the information is available in web applications, for example spammers can artificially prompt products and services via forums [11, 12]. There is no specific technique for detection and prevention spam in forums [8], for this reason, forum information extraction is the first step towards detecting and preventing forum spam.

This information can be of great significance for many businesses but unfortunately, this information is unstructured and distributed. If this information could be extracted, integrated, mined and presented in a right format, it can be an extremely valuable resource.

Business intelligence information can be gathered from this evaluation. It is often seen these days that many companies and organization are trying to integrate backed information to create value e.g. meta search engines, comparative shopping services, gathering market

intelligence, conducting customer behavior analysis and studying product bugs.

For example, Yahoo and Google use the information that posted in forums for improving the quality of search results especially for Q&A queries [9].

Information Extraction (IE) is an area of information technology that uses machine learning techniques to autonomously extract useful information from the Web. IE is used to select desired fields from the given data, by extracting common patterns that appear along with the information. Examples of IE usage are

- ✓ **zoominfo.com**: aggregates information on people in order to allow users enter their target name and shows them title and company which are related to that name,
- ✓ **flipdog.com**: gathers data on jobs and categorizes them based on educational jobs, government jobs, etc; it also shows the jobs related to special city or state. Hence by using this site, users can easily find their proper local job.
- ✓ **CiteSeer.org**: This site extracts number of citation for each academics research paper. This site read the paper reference and increases the paper's citation number for each reference to that paper. It also does duplicates citation entries from papers' reference sections, so you can easily find all the papers that cite a certain paper. So, a graph of citation for a paper can be drawn and fined seminal paper in a subfield, so can listed a related paper for user. Other similar services include extra.info[5], [6].

It is also used in areas such as sale products indexing, job advertisement collection and scientific article collection from the Internet, among several others [7]. Automatically "fill-in" database forms from unstructured data such as Web documents or email is another usage of IE [10]. Since web mining systems retrieve metadata from textual information in Web pages by using IE techniques, it is used in semantic web too [7].

So, we want to use rule based algorithms to extract information from forums.

There are two topics that lead us to make a rule based algorithms, *firstly* the style of forums are changed rarely and all of the template should oblige a same standard, *secondly* the automated IE are usually expensive algorithms.

In this paper we described the different algorithms of forum's Information Extraction. The rest of the paper is organized as follows; first related semi-automatic algorithms will be discussed in section 2. Section 3 introduces an automatic version and finally we conclude the paper in section 4.

II. SEMI-AUTOMATIC APPROACH TO IE

The framework of our IE algorithm contains two steps. We want to extract important information such as author, post content and author number of posts from forums and insert them to database. So this framework can use for forums Information extraction.

In this framework base on forum's version different rules are loaded. The detailed framework is described in the next section.

A. Solution overview

As mentioned in above sections, forums are a big source of information which can be used for analyzing the social behavior, search engine, marketing and so many other aims. We need Information extraction methods for extracting process. There is some forums software that people use them like SMF or phpBB or other ones. The developer, user and programmer have to follow a standard. So, we can use semi-automatic rule based extraction to extract forums base on standard that they used. In other words, we can extract a variety of forums just by one rule, because they used one standard. For example, for extracting most of phpBB version 3.0 we need just one rule. But also there are some templates that have different styles which that we should detect them to extract by different rules. A big picture of our system is shown below in Fig. 1:

Figure.1, A big picture of algorithms

This framework has three components. In the Template & CSS file parser component, we want to parse the version of forum and CSS style then send this information to wrapper for extracting, because wrapper needs different rules for extracting information from different forums. In the wrapper component, based on input file and rules that are saved in the database, we configure the wrapper for extracting file base on its information pattern by rules. In the rule component, the rules for different forums are saved and used for retrieval in the extracting process.

B. Algorithm Description

In this algorithm, forum page addresses or files are passed as input. This file can be downloaded by web downloader like Teleport. This algorithm needs the file address as input and return the post content, author's username and the author's post number as output. Extraction will be done in 3 steps by our algorithm as described below:

Step 1: Extracting Forum Name & Version

In this step, the forum name and version are extracted. Most of forums use signature that describe the style name and also forum's version. This information is extracted by our intelligent parser. Set of rules are applicable in this scenario that help us to make the right decision.

Step 2: Wrapping Html file

In the second step, specific rule based on step 1 is loaded from the database and generates a parser based on this rule and finally runs the parser to extract information from these files. This information is author's username and message.

Step 3: Insert to Database

In the final step, all extracted information is inserted to the database.

III. AUTOMATIC APPROACH TO IE

A. Conceptual Framework for Automatic Information Extraction

We want to extract information from different forums which have used different Html styles. So, algorithms should work independent against Html style. The information features that we want to extract are author, post content and author number of posts. We define a frame work that first analyze the html style of page and extract the html style of message box or table. Then configure the extract engine base on this style to extract information.

B. Solution Overview

As mentioned in above, forums are source of huge and valuable information. Each forum software use different style and even new version of software use different style then previous version. So, problem is a create algorithms that can work independent that html style.

We combined the DOM tree and tree search and similarity algorithms to find a solution to find html style of message separately for each file. We create a tree schema of html tags which each leaf of tree is words or sentences. We use a specific metric to valuation root of sub tree. We sort number of nodes, the same number show the similarity between nodes. If the number of similarity is much and the number is much and thresholds then these sub trees contain users post and replays. In other words, these sub trees are html style of message box. Then we can configure our extraction engine by this html style.

Forums pages are pure web pages from other information. In other means, in the topic pages you can just find some table that messages are listed. So the cases that there is another style are usually not find and similar numbers related to message box.

The big picture of our algorithms is shown below fig.2:

Figure. 2, big picture of our algorithms

We can detect style just by compare the numbers adjust for each node. The way of calculation of each nodes similarity number is describe in below subsection.

1) Similarity metric

We need to introduce metric that make it possible to evaluate percent of similarity between to branch of tree. We use concept of isomorphic graph theory. Finding isomorphic subtrees in a given tree is a standard question of algorithmic graph theory. One modification to this question which has been applied to vast areas in IT engineering is that when we deal with rooted trees and restrict the definition of isomorphism to only rooted trees with same distance from root i.e. their roots are in the same level.

An elegant approach is made for this problem which will be discussed in this note. The main idea is to build the whole partition of isomorphisms between vertices in one iteration. The order this method provides is $O(n)$. a modification to this algorithm yields yet another good result which allows the subtrees to be isomorphic up to some defined level i.e. being isomorphic in k levels and be different from $k+1$ on.

C. Algorithm Description

The forums' file addresses are passed to algorithms as input. Te similarity metrics is calculated for file then style of message body will be found. The style also is passed to extraction engine for IE. So, extraction will be done in 3 steps.

Step 1: Extracting Message Body Html Style

File address is passed to program to calculate the similarity metrics to find html style of message body. In this step, DOM tree of file create and based on isomorphic graph theory, similar sub tree will be detected and pass one of this subtree to extraction engine.

Step 2: Configure IE engine

In this step, IE engine will be configured to extract specific information from file. The engine's parameters will be assigned based on passed style and the engine will be start for IE.

Step 3: Insert to Database

In the final step, all extracted information is inserted to the database.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we proposed a semi-automatic and automatic information extraction algorithm for extracting information from popular discussion boards or forums like SMF, phpBB, vBulletin. WE introduce two important algorithms that aim to detect and extract information from different forums what have different style. In semi-automatic version, the engine is configured by rule that saved in database but in automatic version, html style and rules are founded online then engine is configured for extraction. The time order of automatic algorithm is more than semi-automatic but it can extract data features from each forums.

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